

Contents of Report

Created by <https://lipidomicstandards.org>, version v2.5.0

Direct Infusion Workflow	1
Overall study design	1
Lipid extraction	1
Analytical platform	1
Quality control	1
Method qualification and validation	2
Reporting	2
Sample Descriptions	2
Control/OE Yet3 / Fungi / Cells	2
Lipid Class Descriptions	2
1) ST[M+NH ₄] ⁺ / Lipid identification	2
1) ST[M+NH ₄] ⁺ / Lipid quantification	3

Direct Infusion Workflow

Overall study design

Title of the study	The molecular mechanism of on-demand sterol biosynthesis at organelle contact sites-2		
Document creation date	10/20/2025	Principal investigator	Britta Brügger / Heidelberg Lipidomics
Institution	Heidelberg University Biochemistry Center (BZH)	Corresponding Email	britta.bruegger@bzh.uni-heidelberg.de
Is the workflow targeted or untargeted?	Untargeted	Clinical	No

Lipid extraction

Extraction method	2-phase system	pH adjustment	Hydrochloric acid
2-phase system	Bligh&Dyer	Were internal standards added prior extraction?	Yes

Analytical platform

Ionization additives	Ammonium formate	Detector	Mass spectrometer
MS type	Orbitrap	MS vendor	Thermo
Direct type	Chip	MS Level	MS ¹ , MS ²
Mass resolution for detected ion at MS ¹	High resolution	Resolution at m/z 200 at MS ¹	140000
Mass accuracy in ppm at MS ¹	3	Recording mode of raw data at MS ¹	Profile mode
Mass window for precursor ion isolation (in Da total isolation window)	0.5	Mass resolution for detected ion at MS ²	High resolution
Resolution at m/z 200 at MS ²	140000	Mass accuracy in ppm at MS ²	3
Recording mode of raw data at MS ²	Profile mode	Was/Were additional dimension/techniques used	No

Quality control

Blanks	Yes	Type of Blanks	Internal standard blank
Quality control	No		

Method qualification and validation

Method validation	No
-------------------	----

Reporting

Are reported raw data uploaded into repository?	Available on request	Are metadata available?	Available on request
Raw data upload	Available on request	Additional comments	Raw data will be uploaded to MetaboLights

Sample Descriptions

Control/OE Yet3 / Fungi / Cells

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Provided preanalytical information	Time to freeze, Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Instant sample preparation	No
Time to freeze	between 5 and 40 min	Snap freezing in liquid N2	Yes
Storage temperature	-80 °C	Storage time (month)	0
Freeze-thaw cycles	1	Additives	None
Were samples stored under inert gas?	No	Additional preservation methods	No
Biobank samples	No		

Lipid Class Descriptions

1) ST[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	ST	MS Level for identification	MS ¹ , MS ²
Identification level	Molecular species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M+NH4] ⁺
Isotope correction at MS ¹	Type 2	MS ² adduct	[M] ⁺

Fragments for identification

Fragment name

-FA 2:0(+HO)-Ergosterol(35)

Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ¹ verified by standard	No
MS ² verified by standard	No	Background check at MS ¹	Yes
Background check at MS ²	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Limit of detection	No	Lipid Identification Software	LipidXplorer
Data manipulation	Lock mass correction, Background subtraction	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Nomenclature for fragment ions	No	Further identification remarks	Derivatization of sterols with acetyl chloride to sterol acetate.

1) ST[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Normalization to reference	No
Batch correction	No		